

A TIME-INTEGRATING, REMOTELY MOORED, AUTOMATED SAMPLING AND
CONCENTRATION SYSTEM FOR AQUATIC BUTYLTIN MONITORING

Paul Schatzberg, Carl M. Adema, William M. Thomas, Jr., and Scott R. Mangum

Chemical and Physical Processes Division - Code 283
David Taylor Naval Ship Research and Development Center
Bethesda, Maryland 20084-5000

ABSTRACT

Antifouling hull paints containing tributyltin (TBT) as the active biocide are becoming the coating of choice for pleasure craft and commercial ships. The recent announcement of the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency of a "Special Review of Certain Pesticide Products Containing Tributyltins Used as Antifoulants" will result in an examination of the environmental risks involved in the use of TBT. Therefore, a need exists to monitor harbors and estuaries for nanogram per liter concentrations of TBT and of its substantially less toxic biodegraded decomposition products. One purpose of such a monitoring effort is to determine time-dependent concentration trends at biologically sensitive locations and to apply this information to risk assessment.

We have evaluated a prototype device to help collect such data. This device is self-contained, battery operated, and can be moored remotely. It can be programmed to process volumes of water at various time intervals over several tidal cycles. The water is pumped through a prefilter, an analyte adsorption/concentration column and an integrating flowmeter. The prefilter and adsorption column are replaced periodically and analyzed. This approach permits the determination of a time-integrated average concentration at a particular location.

1. INTRODUCTION

The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency announced in January 1986 its intention to conduct a "Special Review of Certain Pesticide Products Containing Tributyltins Used as Antifoulants."¹ One consequence of this announcement is the increased importance of determining the aquatic concentration of butyltins in harbors and estuaries. The extent of aquatic pollution by a contaminant is defined primarily by sampling and analysis of the water column. Sediment and tissue of local organisms also are analyzed, although these act primarily as long-term integrators and generally follow water column concentrations. Fortunately, methods for ultratrace analysis of nanogram per liter (ng/L) aquatic concentrations of TBT and its degradation products have been developed recently.²⁻⁶ However, water column sampling is time consuming and labor intensive. Current field sampling techniques consist of taking "grab" samples of the water column in 1-liter bottles, and freezing and shipping those bottles to

the laboratory for analysis. Depending on the sample processing rate and the sampling intensity, the frozen sample bottles may have to be stored for months before analysis. In addition, pollutant levels in natural waters show extreme variation with time. Such temporal variations have been particularly well discussed for trace metals⁷⁻¹⁰ and may depend on a variety of factors such as freshwater runoff, sampling depth, tides, currents, and turbulence caused by passage of ships.¹¹ Large temporal variations of organotin concentrations in natural waters have been documented recently.¹² Consequently, the statistically adequate number of grab samples required to describe a particular site accurately often reduces the number of sites that can be measured. Nevertheless, grab sampling offers the most rapid means of conducting an initial survey to establish ambient concentration levels of a suspected toxic substance and then comparing those levels to laboratory bioassay results.

Federal and state agencies are conducting field sampling programs designed to determine TBT concentrations at various sites. The intent is to establish a causal relationship between the activity at these sites, such as marinas, and the concentrations measured. Another purpose is to establish to what extent and at what rate relatively high concentrations at sources distribute to areas that are biologically sensitive. One monitoring goal is to establish time-dependent concentration trends at such sensitive locations and to use this information for assessing risk.

The time-integrating sampling and concentration system described in this paper offers the capability of collecting organotin compounds from estuarine waters over a period of several hours to 4 days. This means that the system averages short-term variations in organotin concentrations. An average concentration provides more stable data than grab samples for detecting long-term trends. The short-term variations can be significant, as has been pointed out. They can make it particularly difficult to detect long-term concentration trends occurring over 1 to 2 years, since such trends frequently represent a small increase or decrease compared to the short-term variability encountered in less than one tidal cycle. Measuring long-term concentration trends (1 to 2 years) is important in establishing the need and extent of regulatory action on the one hand and in determining its effectiveness on the other. A time-integrating system operating over

several tidal cycles at monthly or quarterly intervals would average the variability and provide stable data for trend monitoring. Such data would be difficult and expensive to collect using grab samples. In addition, an average concentration is useful for the verification of mathematical models of harbors and estuaries. Most mathematical models are two-dimensional; that is, they average the concentration of a constituent in the vertical dimension. Vertical variations in concentrations often are quite large for the same reasons mentioned previously. Therefore, in verifying a numerical model, water sampling needs to be performed to minimize or average vertical variations in concentration. The integrating sampler can be used to obtain a vertically averaged concentration by raising and lowering the device through the water column during sample processing. This eliminates the need to take several grab samples at various depths to average the vertical concentration for comparison to the model results.

Additional applications of this time-integrating sampling and concentration system are: (a) Measure concentration trends at or below sublethal effect levels on indigenous organisms, especially near biologically sensitive areas; (b) Measure concentration trends far from sources, at levels substantially below current detection limits, as a means of determining a gradual increase in concentration while still below harmful levels, or a gradual decrease as a consequence of regulatory actions; (c) Integrate expected discharge spikes from known point sources lasting several tidal cycles, determining thereby the total load of pollutant released by that source; and (d) Reduce the frequency of grab sampling by providing time-integrated composite samples.

2. RECENT APPLICATIONS OF TIME-INTEGRATED SAMPLING

The prototype device described in this paper was obtained from Seastar Instruments, Ltd. A similar unit was used recently to measure the concentration of chlorinated hydrocarbons near the Los Angeles ocean outfalls at Whites Point, California.¹³ The device permitted detection limits of approximately 0.05 ng/L for individual compounds. Compounds of the DDT family were found at concentrations up to 2 ng/L. Transplanted mussels were suspended at the monitoring site for 2 months to measure the chlorinated hydrocarbons that bioaccumulate. The transplanted mussels gave results similar to the moored monitoring device for DDT, but very little DDT bioaccumulated. The U.S. Coast Guard recently evaluated the sampling and concentration monitor for hazardous chemicals in the marine environment.¹⁴ The evaluation determined the usefulness of this pollutant monitoring system in hazardous spill response.

3. SAMPLER SYSTEM DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION

The sampling and concentration system was recently described.¹⁵ The unit is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Time-Integrating Sampling and Concentration System Details

It is designed to operate at several hundred meters depth, can process several hundred liters of water without a prefilter and approximately 50 liters with a prefilter, depending on the nature and quantity of the suspended solids. It can maintain flow rates between 50 and 150 mL/min over an extended period of time, usually over several tidal cycles. The unit can utilize a variety of adsorption/extraction columns. The pumping system is microprocessor controlled, which provides large flexibility of cumulative sampling intervals, and precise control of flow rate and sample volume. There are 12 sampling modes and 3 flow rates: 50, 100, and 150 mL/min. The sampler top plate is shown in Figure 2. The unit is self-contained. It is powered by 20 D-cell batteries, which provide 100 hours of continuous pumping. The integrating flowmeter readout is separately powered by a long-life lithium battery.

Figure 2. Time-Integrating Sampler Top Plate

4. FILTER SELECTION

A filter housing utilizing a 142-mm filter disc is contained on the suction side of the sampling pump. The filter is intended to protect the adsorbent from becoming clogged with suspended matter that could inhibit its effectiveness or reduce the flow rate to less than 50 mL/min, at which point the system is designed to stop sampling. Commercially available membrane, polycarbonate, and glass fiber filters were evaluated with Severn River water obtained near the river's mouth to the Chesapeake Bay. There, the river has approximately 1/3 ocean salinity. Depth-type glass fiber filters having a nominal pore size of 0.3 μ m were found to be most effective, assuring the processing of a 20-liter sample having a suspended solids content of 20 mg/L. Based on a limited number of experiments, adsorption of some dissolved organotin compounds on the filter bed is expected. In addition, if any of the analyte is partitioned on suspended particles, some of these particles will be retained on the filter. Consequently, a complete analysis of the natural water processed requires speciation of the organotins collected on the filter as well as on the adsorption column.

5. SELECTION OF THE ADSORBENT

Initial evaluation of a nonpolar macroreticular resin adsorbent, polystyrene divinyl benzene copolymer (XAD-2), demonstrated very poor adsorption for organotin compounds. Consequently, our efforts concentrated on the use of an octadecyl (C18) covalently bonded reversed-phase silica substrate chromatographic adsorbent. This C18/silica adsorbent is readily available from a number of sources. The

mean particle size of this adsorbent generally is about 40 μ m, which is too fine to allow the desired water pumping rates of 50 to 150 mL/min. Therefore, we obtained a C18/silica adsorbent with a particle size range of 0.35 to 0.50 mm.

6. ADSORBENT EVALUATION

The C18/silica adsorbent was evaluated in the laboratory using a 10.5-mm-dia. glass column containing approximately 3.5 g of adsorbent. Small (0.75 liter) and large (10 liter) volumes of synthetic seawater and natural (Severn River) water were spiked with tributyltin chloride, dibutyltin dichloride, and monobutyltin trichloride. The Severn River water contained less than 20 ng/L of organotins. The butyltin chlorides were obtained at 95+% purity from Alfa Chemicals. The effluent was analyzed for organotin by the method of Matthias, et al.² This method consists in the simultaneous hydridization of the alkyltins with sodium borohydride and extraction from the aqueous sample into dichloromethane. The alkyltin hydrides in the extract are separated by packed column gas chromatography and measured by a tin-selective flame photometric detector. For the large volume samples, the first and last 200 mL of the effluent were analyzed. The adsorbent column was eluted with three successive adsorbent volumes of 2% HCl in methanol. An aliquot of the eluent was diluted with synthetic seawater and analyzed.² The averaged results of three replicates are shown in Tables 1 and 2. The spiked values have a precision of +1%. The effluent and eluent values for the di- and tributyltin chlorides have a precision of +20% and +40% for the monobutyltin chloride. These laboratory results show that the C18/silica adsorbent is effective in quantitatively collecting and eluting di- and tributyltin chlorides but not monobutyltin chloride.

Table 1. Organotin Measured in Low-Volume (0.75 L) Samples of Synthetic Seawater and Natural (Severn River) Water

Type of Butyltin Chloride	Quantity Spiked (μ g)	Effluent (μ g)	Eluent (μ g)	Recovery (%)
<u>Synthetic Seawater</u>				
Mono-	2.38	0.57	0.76	32
Di-	2.56	0.05	2.87	112
Tri-	2.74	0.05	2.58	94
<u>Natural Water</u>				
Mono-	2.38	0.95	1.59	67
Di-	2.56	0.10	2.25	88
Tri-	2.74	ND*	2.60	95

*ND = organotin not detected.

Table 2. Organotin Measured in High-Volume (10 L) Samples of Synthetic Seawater and Natural (Severn River) Water

Type of Butyltin Chloride	Quantity Spiked (µg)	Effluent (µg)		Eluent (µg)	Recovery (%)
		First 100 mL	Second 100 mL		
<u>Synthetic Seawater</u>					
Mono-	2.38	0.71	0.14	0.57	24
Di-	2.56	ND*	0.10	2.05	80
Tri-	2.74	ND	ND	2.88	105
<u>Natural Water</u>					
Mono-	2.38	0.43	0.21	0.67	28
Di-	2.56	0.15	ND	2.87	112
Tri-	2.74	ND	ND	3.15	115

*ND = organotin not detected.

When larger quantities of the C18/silica adsorbent were used, namely, 45 g, the chromatograms obtained from the analytical procedure showed evidence of redistribution of some of the analyte into other unidentified peaks. This might be caused by isolated, non-hydrogen-bridged, highly acidic SiOH groups found in otherwise stable silica-based chromatographic materials, as discussed in a recent paper.¹⁶ This problem could be solved by identifying a means to permanently neutralize the highly acidic and active SiOH groups as part of the normal conditioning step in preparing the adsorbent. An immediate practical solution was to use substantially less than the maximum quantity of adsorbent in view of its relatively high capacity. It appeared that 8 to 10 grams of adsorbent were sufficient for processing 20 or more liters of natural water, even when they contained microgram per liter concentrations of alkyltins. With those quantities of adsorbent, the effect observed with the much larger quantity of adsorbent could still be seen, but at an acceptable level. A typical chromatogram resulting from the use of 8.5 grams of adsorbent is shown in Figure 3.

7. TIME-INTEGRATING SYSTEM EVALUATION

The time-integrating system was evaluated in the laboratory as follows. Ten liters of synthetic seawater were spiked with dibutyltin dichloride and tributyltin chloride. The water was pumped through the unit at 100 mL/min with a glass fiber filter in place. After the 10 liters had been processed, the filter was removed and treated with dichloromethane in a Soxhlet extractor for 18 hours. The solvent was processed in accordance with the analytical procedure.² The adsorbent was eluted and the eluent analyzed as before. The results are shown in Table 3. The effluent, filter, and eluent values have a precision of +20%. These results show that quantitative recovery by the system from aqueous solution is very good, but requires combining results from the filter and eluent. Field evaluation of the system is underway at the writing of this paper and will continue over the next several months.

Figure 3. Typical Chromatogram from Time-Integrated Eluent Sample

Table 3. Laboratory Evaluation of the System

Quantity Spiked (µg)	System Effluent (µg)	Filter (µg)	Eluent (µg)	Filter plus Eluent (µg)	Recovery (%)
<u>Dibutyltin Dichloride</u>					
13.23	0.34	6.0	8.2	14.2	107
<u>Tributyltin Chloride</u>					
13.06	0.064	3.3	9.2	12.5	96

8. CONCLUSION

The time-integrating sampling and concentration systems is operational and feasible for application to monitoring for organotin concentrations in harbors and estuaries. It can provide a time-integrated average organotin concentration over several tidal cycles and offers a number of alternatives and advantages over "grab" sampling as part of an overall monitoring strategy.

9. REFERENCES

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